

FLEXURAL FRACTURE MECHANISM OF CARBON/ARAMID HYBRID
UNIDIRECTIONAL FRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the flexural fracture behavior of carbon/aramid hybrid unidirectional FRP laminates (C/A hybrid FRP) in which CFRP layer was sandwiched between two AFRP layers, three point bending tests for C/A hybrid FRP as well as CFRP and AFRP were conducted at various constant temperatures. As results, the flexural fracture behavior of C/A hybrid FRP is classified into two modes by temperature. One is the compressive fracture of CFRP layer in the range of high temperature where the flexural strength decreases with temperature remarkably. The other is the tensile fracture of AFRP layer in the range of low temperature where the flexural strength changes scarcely with temperature. Furthermore, the flexural fracture behavior of C/A hybrid FRP predicted by the laminated beam theory using the mechanical properties of CFRP and AFRP agree approximately with the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: Fiber Reinforced Plastics; Carbon Fiber; Aramid Fiber; Hybrid; Laminate; Flexural Behavior; Failure Criterion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently the fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) using carbon or aramid fibers have come to be used as structural components of spaceships etc. Each of these fibers has its own advantages and disadvantages from the viewpoint

of mechanical properties such as elastic modulus, tensile strength and ultimate strain, e.g. carbon fibers have high elastic modulus and high tensile strength but low ultimate strain. On the other hand aramid fibers have high ultimate strain, though elastic modulus and tensile strength are lower than carbon fibers^{1,2}. A hybrid FRP consisting of more than two kinds of fibers which have different mechanical properties have rapidly developed, aiming at improved mechanical properties.

In the application of hybrid FRP to the structural components there are two factors which have significant effects upon the mechanical properties of hybrid FRP. One is laminate constitution as the structural factor and the other is time and temperature as the environmental factor. The influence of laminate constitution on the mechanical properties of hybrid FRP has been already reported in many papers³⁻⁶. On the other hand there are very few papers about the influence of time and temperature, although this influence on hybrid FRP should be naturally predicted because the matrix resin shows viscoelastic behavior⁷⁻¹⁰.

In this paper, a carbon/aramid hybrid unidirectional FRP laminates (C/A hybrid FRP) in which carbon FRP (CFRP) layer was sandwiched between two aramid FRP (AFRP) layers was prepared. Three point bending tests of C/A hybrid FRP as well as CFRP and AFRP were conducted at various constant temperatures. The flexural fracture behavior of C/A hybrid FRP obtained experimentally was compared with the theoretical ones predicted by the laminated beam theory using the mechanical properties of CFRP and AFRP.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Preparation of Specimens Two kinds of fibers were prepared. One is carbon fibers, BESFIGHT 6000 made by Toho Rayon Ltd. and the other is aramid fibers, KEVLAR 49 made by Du Pont Co. Ltd. The formations and properties of these fibers are shown in Table 1. The laminated plates were molded by compression forming of the prepreg sheets of epoxy resin (thickness 0.2 mm) in which the fibers of carbon or aramid were unidirectionally arranged. Three kinds of laminate constitution molded are CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP as shown in Figure 1. The number of layer is 15 and the thickness of plate is 3 mm for all kinds of plate. The volume fraction of fibers in these plates is approximately 52-55%.

2.2 Test Procedures Three point bending tests for CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP were conducted by using the Instron type universal testing machine equipped with a constant temperature test chamber. The thickness, width and length of all specimens are 3 mm, 10 mm and 100 mm, respec-

tively. The span is 60 mm. All of the tests were performed at various constant temperatures between room temperature and 120 °C. The deflection rate at loading point was 2 mm/min.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Load-deflection Diagrams Typical load-deflection diagrams of CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP are shown in Figure 2. The diagrams of CFRP are roughly linear until maximum load and the loads drop suddenly at maximum load for all temperatures. On the other hand, the diagrams of AFRP show nonlinear behavior beyond knee point although these diagrams are roughly linear until knee point. A sudden load drop at maximum load was not observed at temperature $T = 120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The diagrams of C/A hybrid FRP show slightly nonlinear behavior until the maximum load which are not so remarkable comparing with that on the diagram of AFRP.

3.2 Fracture Mechanisms Figure 3 shows the fractographs of CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP just after the maximum load at room temperature, 60 °C and 120 °C. Observing these fractographs, it is clear that the fracture of CFRP for all temperatures is the compressive fracture generated by the trigger of micro-buckling of fibers in the surface layer on compression side of specimen, and that the fracture of AFRP is the tensile fracture by the cut of fibers in the surface layer on tension side of specimen in the range of low temperature. However, the plastic deformation on compression side grows remarkably with increasing temperature, and the tensile fracture on tension side of specimen can not be apparently observed in the range of high temperature. The fracture of C/A hybrid FRP is controlled by two fracture modes. One is the tensile fracture of the surface AFRP layer on tension side at low temperature and the other is the compressive fracture of the most out CFRP layer on compression side at high temperature.

3.3 Flexural Strengths The relations of the flexural strength σ_b against temperature for CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP are shown in Figure 4. The flexural strength of CFRP is considerably larger than that of AFRP over all range of temperature. The flexural strengths of CFRP and AFRP decrease with temperature. The hollow circular symbols on the flexural strength of C/A hybrid FRP show the tensile fracture of the surface AFRP layer in tension side of specimen and the solid circular symbols, the compressive fracture of the most out CFRP layer in compression side of specimen. The flexural fracture of C/A hybrid FRP is the tensile fracture of AFRP layer in the range of low temperature where the flexural strength changes scarcely with temperature. The flexural fracture of C/A hybrid

FRP is the compressive fracture of CFRP layer in the range of high temperature where the flexural strength decreases with temperature.

4. PREDICTION

4.1 Deformation and Failure Criteria The deformation and failure criteria of C/A hybrid FRP based upon the laminated beam theory using the tensile and compressive behavior of CFRP and AFRP are proposed.

The stress-strain diagram of CFRP is shown in Figure 5(a). The diagram of CFRP under tensile and compressive loads is roughly linear between tensile strength σ_{CT} and compressive strength $\sigma_{CC}(T)$. The specimen fractures suddenly at σ_{CT} or $\sigma_{CC}(T)$. On the other hand the stress-strain diagram of AFRP is shown in Figure 5(b). The diagram of AFRP under tensile and compressive loads is roughly linear between tensile strength σ_{AT} and compressive yield stress $\sigma_{AY}(T)$. The specimen fractures suddenly at σ_{AT} , but the specimen yields at $\sigma_{AY}(T)$ and keeps constant stress of $\sigma_{AY}(T)$ with the increase of strain.

It is well known that Young's moduli E_C , E_A and tensile strength σ_{CT} , σ_{AT} change scarcely with temperature and here the results obtained under room temperature are to be referred. But as far as compressive strength $\sigma_{CC}(T)$ and compressive yield stress $\sigma_{AY}(T)$ are concerned, the experiment of this time shows remarkable temperature dependency and such results are referred in the following prediction. The temperature dependencies on the mechanical properties of CFRP and AFRP used in the following prediction are shown in Figure 6.

The stress and strain distributions in C/A hybrid FRP can be assumed as shown in Figure 7, if C/A hybrid FRP is considered to be the laminated beam consisting of CFRP and AFRP layers which are assumed to hold the mechanical behavior as shown in Figure 5. It is assumed that the flexural fracture of C/A hybrid FRP occurs when the stress in the surface AFRP layer on tension side reaches the tensile strength σ_{AT} of AFRP or the stress in the most out CFRP layer on compression side reaches the compressive strength $\sigma_{CC}(T)$ of CFRP.

4.2 Comparison of the Theoretical Results with Experimental Results

Typical load-deflection diagrams of C/A hybrid FRP are shown in Figure 8. The solid and dotted lines in this figure show the theoretical and experimental results, respectively. From Figure 8 it is clear that the theoretical and experimental deformations agree fairly well with each other.

The flexural strengths of C/A hybrid FRP obtained from the maximum load of load-deflection diagram (Figure 8) are shown against temperature in Figure 9. The hollow and solid symbols in this figure show the experimental results of the tensile fracture of AFRP layer and the compressive fracture of CFRP layer, respectively and the dotted and solid thin lines show the theoretical results of two fracture modes mentioned above. From Figure 9 it can be seen both theoretically and experimentally that fracture mode changes from tensile fracture of AFRP layer to compressive fracture of CFRP layer as temperature rises. However, the flexural strengths predicted are lower than the experimental results in the vicinity of room temperature. The solid and dotted thin lines in Figure 10 show the compressive strength $\sigma_{CC}(T)$ of CFRP and the tensile strength σ_{AT} of AFRP used for the above prediction, respectively. If these strengths rose up to thick lines in this figure, the flexural strengths of C/A hybrid FRP would be expressed as thick lines in Figure 9, and these ideal results coincide with the experimental results. The advantage of the ideal fracture strength to the theoretical ones in the vicinity of low temperature in Figure 9 can be considered to be so-called "hybrid effect", and this advantage introduces to the concept that the proposed deformation and failure criteria are applicable to the material design of C/A hybrid FRP.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A carbon/aramid hybrid unidirectional FRP laminates (C/A hybrid FRP) in which CFRP layer was sandwiched between two AFRP layers was prepared. Three point bending tests of C/A hybrid FRP as well as CFRP and AFRP were conducted at various constant temperatures. The flexural fracture behavior of C/A hybrid FRP obtained experimentally was compared with the predicted ones by the proposed deformation and failure criteria. The results are summarized as followings:

- (1) The flexural fracture behavior of C/A hybrid FRP changes remarkably with temperature.
- (2) The flexural fracture of C/A hybrid FRP is classified clearly into two modes by temperature. One is the compressive fracture of CFRP layer in the range of high temperature where the flexural strength decreases with temperature remarkably. The other is the tensile fracture of AFRP layer in the range of low temperature where the flexural strength changes scarcely with temperature.
- (3) The flexural fracture behavior of C/A hybrid FRP predicted by the laminated beam theory using the mechanical properties of CFRP and AFRP agree approximately with the experimental results. Therefore, the proposed deformation and failure criteria are applicable to the material design of C/A hybrid FRP.

6. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1 Formations and properties of fibers.

	Carbon	Aramid
Diameter of mono filament (μm)	7	13
Filament number in 1 yarn	6000	1520
Elastic modulus (GPa)	235	127
Tensile strength (GPa)	3.04	2.94
Ultimate strain (%)	1.3	2.3
Specific gravity	1.77	1.45

Type	C	A	A-C-A
Illustration of lamination			
Number of layers CFRP/AFRP	15/0	0/15	7/8

CFRP layer AFRP layer
 FIGURE 1 Laminate constitutions of FRP.

FIGURE 2 Load-deflection diagrams.

FIGURE 3 Fracture appearances of CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP.

FIGURE 4 Temperature dependence on flexural strengths of CFRP, AFRP and C/A hybrid FRP.

FIGURE 5 Stress-strain diagrams of CFRP and AFRP.

FIGURE 6 Temperature dependence on mechanical properties of CFRP and AFRP.

FIGURE 7 Stress and strain distribution models in C/A hybrid FRP.

FIGURE 8 Load-deflection diagrams of C/A hybrid FRP.

FIGURE 9 Comparison of ideal, theoretical and experimental values on flexural strength of C/A hybrid FRP.

FIGURE 10 Comparison of ideal and experimental values on compressive strength of CFRP and tensile strength of AFRP.

